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Native aquatic plastispheres in a river–wastewater catchment: structural and microbial characterization using microscopy and culture-based methods

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ABSTRACT

Plastispheres, microbial biofilms formed on plastics, are increasingly recognized as complex ecological niches capable of transporting both chemical pollutants and pathogenic microorganisms. Current research on plastispheres relies heavily on controlled lab or *in situ* experiments. The aim of the study was to characterize the culturable bacterial fraction and their antibiotic resistance, as well as to observe the surface of the plastispheres developing on native field-collected plastic debris from river and treated wastewater within a single catchment. The study employs an interdisciplinary approach combining microbial culturing, molecular analyses, scanning electron and fluorescence microscopy and spectroscopy. We observed heterogeneous microbial colonization density across the plastic particles by heterotrophic bacteria. Carbapenem resistance in aquatic plastispheres was determined by intrinsic mechanisms, rather than mobile, clinically significant carbapenemases. *Aeromonas hydrophila* exhibited multidrug resistance and carried the *bla*_{C_{phA} carbapenemase genes. Microscopy revealed structurally complex and spatially heterogeneous biofilms composed of bacterial clusters, diatoms, and highly-expansive fungal structures that appeared adapted for plastic colonization. Observations from native plastispheres enhance our understanding of naturally aged plastic debris and may serve as a reference point for studies based on *in situ* experiments. Our findings support further research using advanced imaging and molecular approaches to assess functional and resistance-related potential.}

Keywords

antibiotic resistance; confocal microscopy; FTIR spectroscopy; microplastic particles; SEM; biofilm; carbapenemase

1. Introduction

Plastic pollution is a serious and growing global problem. Recent estimates suggest that global plastic production could potentially triple from its 2019 value of 353 Mt to 1,014 Mt by 2060 (OECD, 2022). Furthermore, the current use of plastics is far from circular, and generates substantial amounts of plastic waste that ultimately end up in the environment. It has been estimated that in 2019, the leakage of macroplastics from mismanaged waste into aquatic environments amounted to 6.1 Mt; this value is projected to potentially double to 11.6 Mt by 2060. A similar trend can be observed in the accumulated stock of plastics in aquatic environments, with current estimates of 109 Mt in rivers and lakes and 30 Mt in oceans expected to increase twofold (348 Mt) and fivefold (145 Mt), respectively, by 2060 (OECD, 2022). In recent years, increasing attention has been paid to plastispheres, i.e. microbial biofilms that develop and evolve on the surface of plastics in the environment. This has led to a shift in the perception of plastic pollution, which is now often viewed not only as a chemical or physical pollutant but also as a biological vector. The plastic debris itself is increasingly understood as a substrate carrying a complex (micro)biological load. As a result, plastispheres have become the subject of growing scientific interest, especially in studies focusing on the ecology, environmental impact and potential risks associated with the microbial communities inhabiting these microhabitats (Li et al., 2024; Ridley et al., 2024).

Freshwater systems are currently the largest global aquatic reservoirs of plastic pollution, being responsible for 78.41% of total pollution in 2019, and this is expected to continue, with the predicted values reaching 70.58% by 2060 (OECD, 2022). This is of particular concern, as plastics in rivers, including those entering from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) may account for up to 81.25% of all plastic pollution ultimately reaching the oceans. The plastispheres on particles bound for marine environments are initially formed in freshwater and wastewater systems, where the particles can acquire complex microbial and chemical signatures. Despite the scale and significance of plastic pollution in freshwater systems, the fate and composition of plastispheres in rivers and wastewater environments remain relatively understudied compared to marine settings (Bocci et al., 2024). This gap is especially notable given the potential of wastewater plastispheres to act as integrated vectors of microbial and chemical contamination. Wastewater is known to carry high loads of both antibiotics and resistant bacteria (Mutuku et al., 2022) which may form complex plastispheres when combined with microplastics that can represent a multifaceted environmental threat. Importantly, embedding within biofilms on plastic surfaces may provide bacteria with an escape route from wastewater treatment, as an alternative to adopting free-living planktonic forms; this is of particular concern for pathogenic and antibiotic-resistant strains. This biofilm-associated mode of dispersal may enhance their environmental persistence, resistance to stressors, and potential for colonization in downstream ecosystems (Silva et al., 2023, 2024).

Plastisphere studies rely on three main methodological approaches: field collection of environmental plastic, *in situ* experiments, and *ex situ* laboratory setups. Each of these approaches offers distinct research opportunities and limitations (Shruti et al., 2024). Of these, the most common approach is the *in situ* experiment; these typically involve exposing standardized plastic materials to natural environments, allowing for partial control over parameters such as polymer type, shape, and exposure time (Lear et al., 2022). While lacking experimental control, the plastics collected in the field reflect the most realistic environmental plastispheres, as they are formed under complex and often undocumented exposure histories. In contrast, *ex situ* systems provide the highest level of reproducibility but the lowest ecological relevance (Monràs-Riera et al., 2024).

Similarly, the microbial analyses of plastispheres typically involves two complementary strategies: culture-independent (metagenomic) and culture-based methods (Shruti et al., 2024). Metagenomics enables broad profiling of microbial communities, including uncultivable taxa, and can reveal the presence of antibiotic-resistant pathogens or potential plastic degraders. Culture-based techniques serve as a complement by allowing functional analyses, phenotyping, and whole-genome sequencing of viable isolates. These can be further supplemented with microscope-based techniques, particularly scanning

electron microscopy (SEM) and fluorescence microscopy, to provide spatial visualization of biofilm structure and reveal live cells embedded in deeper layers (Arias-Andres, 2020; Schlundt et al., 2020). Together, these tools enable a multi-dimensional understanding of plastispheres as complex and dynamic microbial ecosystems.

The multifaceted interaction between plastic, microbial biofilms and the surrounding environment necessitates an interdisciplinary research approach (Shruti et al., 2024). It is important to integrate microbiology, environmental chemistry, and imaging techniques to fully assess both the ecological roles and risks associated with plastispheres. The present study combines classical microbiological culture with molecular methods, SEM and fluorescence microscopy, as well as spectroscopy, to comprehensively characterize plastispheres present in riverine and wastewater environments. This approach enabled a clear visualization of biofilm structure and its spatial distribution on plastic surfaces, isolation of active bacterial cells and a clear identification of the plastic matrix itself.

Current research on plastispheres relies heavily on controlled lab or *in situ* experiments. This limited approach often fails to capture long-term, dynamic colonization, prompting calls for real-world environmental models (Huang et al., 2024). Our study addresses this gap. By analyzing naturally aged plastic debris (native plastispheres) retrieved from aquatic environments, we provide ecologically relevant insights into the actual structural and characteristics of the plastisphere, offering a crucial reference point for the field.

The aim of this study was to conduct a comprehensive, interdisciplinary characterization of plastisphere communities formed on plastic debris collected *in situ* from river water and wastewater, these being two underexplored but environmentally-relevant aquatic environments. The study takes an ecohydrology approach, by integrating catchment-scale processes to better understand the occurrence, distribution, and microbial colonization of plastics in river and wastewater systems. The research was conducted within the catchment of the Pilica River; the material included multiple plastic particles collected from water sampling sites along the river continuum, as well as from treated wastewater obtained from secondary clarifiers. By focusing on naturally-formed plastispheres on environmental plastics, this study contributes novel insights into microbial colonization under realistic conditions using an integrative analytical approach to plastisphere research. Our primary objective was to isolate and characterize metabolically active, viable, and drug-resistant bacteria to identify potential threats, focusing specifically on carbapenemase-producing organisms currently recognized as the most critical drug-resistant bacteria (Sati et al., 2025). Concurrently, we monitored the general microbiological background by analyzing the quantity of bacteria growing at 22 and 37 °C on general purpose media. To our knowledge, no previous studies have combined SEM and fluorescence microscopy to examine field-collected plastic particles from river and wastewater. This integrative approach opens the way for more advanced and detailed investigations of biofilm formation on plastics.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Area and Sample Collection

Material was collected in the catchment area (9258 km²) of the Pilica River, situated in central Poland in July 2024 (Figure 1A). The Pilica River itself is 342 km long and constitutes the largest left-bank tributary of the Vistula River, the longest river in Poland and one of the main contributors to the Baltic Sea (Kiedrzyńska et al., 2014). The sampling sites were evenly distributed along the course of the river, extending from its upper reaches to its confluence with the Vistula River. The study focused on wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) discharging treated wastewater into the Pilica River catchment. The WWTPs included in the analysis were classified as small-scale (0–1,999 population equivalent [PE]), medium-scale (2,000–9,999 PE), and large-scale plants (15,000–99,000 PE) according to the Regulation of 12 July 2019 issued by the Minister of Maritime Economy and Inland Navigation (Journal of Laws, 2019).

Visible plastic fragments were collected at the WWTP sites using sieves mounted on extendable arms (Figure 2B; Figure S1A,B,C); sample collection was directed towards any visible plastic particles that were floating on the surface of the secondary clarifiers (Figure S1D,E). In contrast, sample collection from river sites was more demanding and required a multi-method approach. At each location, three complementary techniques were employed: (1) filtering five liter samples of river water through a fine mesh, (2) submerging a sieve directly into the river current for a set period of time, and (3) collecting particles that had naturally accumulated along the riverbanks or become entangled in natural obstacles such as vegetation, stones or debris (Figure 2B; Figure S1F). Following each sampling event, any visible plastic particles retained on the sieves were manually extracted using tweezers for further analysis.

Research material was successfully collected from a total of 14 sampling sites, including eight WWTPs and six locations along the Pilica River (Figure 2A), yielding a total of 74 plastic particles (Figure S2). The samples were taken directly from the sampling sites and stored in sterile Falcon tubes, immersed in the original medium from which they were collected, under refrigerated conditions. The material was transported to the laboratory and was subjected to parallel analyses, *viz.* microbiological, microscopic, and spectroscopic approaches, analyzed on the same day as sampling (Figure 2C).

Figure 1 Overview of the Pilica River catchment (central Poland) - study area, sampling sites, and collected plastic material. **A**- Locations of plastic sampling sites in riverine environments and wastewater treatment plants. For the wastewater facilities, the size category of each plant is indicated (Serwecińska et al., 2021 modified); **B**- Field Sampling Examples: Presentation of field material collection for a sample site for wastewater and river, with examples of plastic particles collected from the investigated medium; **C**- Research scheme. Collected plastic particles were color-coded based on their origin: red - wastewater, blue - river. The number of particles subjected to specific analyses is indicated (N=x). In the first stage, the samples were subjected to three forms of analysis. The initial analyses were complemented by additional analyses to achieve an integrated multidisciplinary approach. MALDI-TOF: Matrix-Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionization Time-of-Flight Mass Spectrometry; SEM: Scanning Electron Microscopy; CLSM: Confocal Laser Scanning Microscopy; LM: Light Microscopy.

2.2. Physicochemical Characterization of Sampling Sites

In situ physicochemical measurements were performed at all 14 sampling sites during sampling to characterize their respective environments. Temperature (T), dissolved oxygen (DO), electrical conductivity (EC), salinity (Sal) and redox potential (ORP) were determined using a YSI-6050000 Professional Plus multiparameter instrument. Turbidity (Turb) was measured using the 2100Qis Portable Turbidimeter (Hach).

2.3. Isolation of bacteria from plastic particles

The first step in the microbiological analysis was to quantify the number of bacteria present on the plastic particles. For this stage, particles were selected from both wastewater and river environments, with equal proportions from the two; also, a wide range of sampling sites, sizes and colors were included. A total of 30 particles were analyzed according to the workflow shown in Figure 2C. Each particle was gently rinsed three times with sterile saline solution to remove loosely-attached debris.

Following this, the biofilm was extracted from the plastic surface by sonication followed by vortexing with glass beads: an approach recommended for isolating culturable bacteria from plastispheres (Stevenson et al., 2023). The resulting suspension was subjected to microbiological plating and Gram-staining for light microscopy. The biofilm suspension was serially diluted at 1:10, 1:100 and 1:1000 ratios. Both the undiluted suspension and its dilutions were plated in triplicate onto tryptic soy agar (TSA) and incubated at 22 °C and 37 °C, as well as onto mSuperCARBA™ (CHROMagar™) medium incubated at 37 °C. After 24 hours of incubation, the colonies were counted and the bacterial load per particle was calculated based on the plating results.

Following microbiological plating, 9–10 colonies were selected from each particle, re-streaked, and cultured for further analyses, the aim being to obtain approximately equal number of colonies from each type of agar medium and incubation condition (82 isolates from TSA incubated at 22°C, 83 isolates from TSA at 37°C, and 90 isolates from CARBA medium) (Table S1). From the CARBA medium, colored colonies were selected where possible, as these were indicated by the manufacturer to belong to the Enterobacteriaceae family (Figure S3). Two of the tested particles did not demonstrate any bacterial growth on mSuperCARBA™ medium and were excluded: one from wastewater (12.6.W) and one from the river (11.1.R). Therefore, 256 isolates derived from 28 particles were selected for further analysis. These isolates were frozen and stored in LB broth supplemented with glycerol for downstream investigations.

The plastic particles (N=30) were subsequently characterised by light microscopy and Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, along with surface measurements (Figure 2C).

2.4. Identification of Bacteria Using MALDI-TOF MS

The bacterial strains were streaked onto tryptic soy agar (TSA) plates (Merck, Germany) for propagation. Despite multiple attempts, 57 strains initially selected for further analysis could not be re-cultured; consequently, 199 strains were advanced to the identification stage (Table S1). The strains were identified using Matrix-Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionization Time-of-Flight Mass Spectrometry (MALDI-TOF MS) with a Vitek MS system (bioMérieux, France). Briefly, a single colony of each strain was re-streaked onto TSA and incubated at 37 ± 1 °C for 24 hours. Each colony was then transferred to a single spot on the MALDI-TOF target plate using an inoculating loop, then overlaid with 1 µL of matrix solution (α -cyano-4-hydroxycinnamic acid; bioMérieux, France), and air-dried completely. Identification results were considered valid only if the analysis yielded a high-confidence score (≥ 2.00). A total of 181 isolates met this criterion.

2.5. Screening for Carbapenem-Resistant Bacteria

To screen for potential carbapenem-resistant strains, the bacterial biomass grown on TSA was subjected to antibiotic susceptibility testing on Mueller-Hinton (Thermo Scientific™ Oxoid™, USA) agar following EUCAST guidelines (EUCAST, 2025), using 10 µg imipenem discs. The testing was performed for all 199 strains, originating from both general-purpose media and mSuperCARBA™ selective media. At this stage, strains were preliminarily classified as carbapenem-resistant if they exhibited an inhibition zone diameter of <19 mm (n=30), and as susceptible if the inhibition zone was ≥ 19 mm (n=169).

2.6. DNA Isolation and Bacterial Strain Identification Based on 16S rRNA Gene Sequencing

Strains preliminarily classified as carbapenem resistant (n=30), and isolates with low-confidence identification scores in MALDI-TOF MS analysis (n=18), were selected for identification based on 16S rRNA gene sequencing. Genomic DNA was extracted from bacterial cultures using a heat-shock method (Dashti et al., 2009). The 16S rRNA was subjected to PCR amplification using universal primers F27 and R1492 according to Lane (1991). PCR products were purified using an EPPiC Fast DNA Purification Kit (A&A Biotechnology, Gdańsk, Poland) and sent for sequencing to Macrogen Europe (Amsterdam, The Netherlands). The obtained sequences were compared against available databases using the BLAST tool. Following MALDI-ToF analysis and 16S rRNA gene sequencing, 129 isolates were successfully identified to the species level, and 70 were identified to the genus level (Figure S4).

The confirmed and updated identification data were cross-referenced with reference tables, completing the dataset on carbapenem-resistant strains. The inhibition zone diameters were compared to EUCAST reference breakpoints (EUCAST, 2025). For strains identified as *Aeromonas* spp., susceptibility to imipenem was evaluated based on the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines for antimicrobial dilution and disk susceptibility testing of infrequently isolated or fastidious bacteria (CLSI M45, 2016), due to the absence of corresponding EUCAST breakpoints (EUCAST, 2025). In total, 30 isolates were confirmed as carbapenem-resistant (Table S1).

2.7. Antibiotic Susceptibility Testing of Carbapenem-Resistant Isolates

Isolates confirmed to be carbapenem resistant (n=30) were subjected to additional antibiotic susceptibility testing using the disk diffusion method, following EUCAST guidelines (EUCAST, 2025) (Table S2). The *Aeromonas* spp. isolates were tested using antibiotic discs (Thermo Scientific™ Oxoid™) containing ceftazidime (10 µg), aztreonam (30 µg), ciprofloxacin (5 µg), and trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole (1.25/23.75 µg). For *Pseudomonas* spp. isolates, discs containing piperacillin (30 µg), ceftazidime (10 µg), aztreonam (30 µg), ciprofloxacin (5 µg), and tobramycin (10 µg) were applied. For *Stenotrophomonas* spp. isolates, trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole (1.25/23.75 µg) discs were used.

2.8. Detection of Antibiotic Resistance Genes by PCR

Genomic DNA from bacterial strains confirmed as carbapenem resistant was subjected to PCR amplification targeting 14 carbapenemase-encoding genes: *bla*_{KPC}, *bla*_{NDM}, *bla*_{OXA-48}, *bla*_{VIM}, *bla*_{IMP}, *bla*_{SPM}, *bla*_{AIM}, *bla*_{GIM}, *bla*_{BIC}, *bla*_{SIM}, *bla*_{DIM}, *bla*_{GES}, *bla*_{IMI/NMC} and *bla*_{Cpha/IMIS}. Primer sequences and PCR conditions are provided in Table S3 (Henriques et al., 2006; Hong et al., 2012; Poirel et al., 2011).

2.9. Microscopic Imaging

Selected plastic particles (n=4) were subjected to SEM and CLSM observations. For CLSM analysis, plastic fragments were prepared under sterile conditions and placed in a 96-well plate for staining, utilizing the LIVE/DEAD™ BacLight™ Bacterial Viability Kit (Invitrogen). The microorganisms on the surface of the materials were stained with a dye mixture in a final volume of 200 µL, in the dark for 15 minutes. Following staining, excess dye was removed by transferring the fragments to a new well and rinsing them with sterile phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). After rinsing, the samples were mounted between two coverslips and imaged using a confocal microscope. The analysis was performed with a Leica TCS SP8 confocal laser scanning microscope (Leica Microsystems, Wetzlar, Germany) equipped with a 63×/1.40 oil immersion objective (HC PL APO CS2). The excitation and emission maxima were approximately 480/500 nm for SYTO 9 and 490/635 nm for propidium iodide. Live microorganisms appeared green. Images were captured and processed using the Leica Application Suite X (LAS X, Leica Microsystems, Germany) software.

The same plastic particles were also examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The fragments were transferred directly onto standard stubs (ø 12.5 mm), mounted in a temperature-

controlled sample holder, and frozen at -10°C . Imaging was performed using a Phenom ProX scanning electron microscope (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., Waltham, USA).

Following the microbiological analyses, the plastic particles ($n=30$) and the biofilm suspensions detached from them ($n=30$) were subjected to light microscope analysis; the suspension was obtained by vortexing and sonication and then subjected to Gram-staining for analysis ($n=30$). The analysis was performed using a Nexcope NE620 light microscope (Delta Optical) equipped with a DLT-Cam PRO 1080 camera (Delta Optical).

2.10. Polymer Identification by FTIR and Assessment of Particle Size and Surface Area

All analyzed particles ($n=74$) were imaged using mosaic imaging with a Nicolet™ iN10 Infrared Microscope (Thermo Scientific™) and a stereomicroscope (Delta Optical). Particle length and surface area were measured with a calibrated scale using ImageJ software (Schroeder et al., 2021); the analysis was performed as described previously (Valente et al., 2023). The particles were classified into three categories based on their size: microplastics ($<5\text{ mm}$), mesoplastics (5 mm to 2.5 cm), and macroplastics ($>2.5\text{ cm}$) (Jeyasanta et al., 2020).

After microbiological and microscopic analyses, the particles were treated with a hydrogen peroxide solution (35%) to remove organic contaminants that could affect the quality of FTIR spectra. Their polymer composition was then determined using a Nicolet™ iN10 Infrared Microscope (Thermo Scientific). The measurements were performed in reflection mode on gold-coated microscope slides. Data acquisition and analysis were carried out using OMNIC Picta Software (Thermo Scientific). Only spectra showing a similarity match of $\geq 80\%$ with the reference library were considered a successful identification. If necessary, the particles were cut into smaller and thinner fragments with a scalpel to improve identification quality.

2.11. Calculations, Statistical Analyses and Data Visualization

The bacterial abundance per unit area (CFU/mm^2) was calculated based on the values obtained for total number of bacteria per particle and for surface area. The surface area values obtained from the images were multiplied by two to account for both sides of the particle, i.e. not just the side visible in the image.

Network analysis was conducted using Gephi 0.9 (Bastian et al., 2009). A 16S rRNA gene sequence similarity dendrogram was generated by multiple sequence alignment using Clustal W (Larkin et al., 2007) and annotated with iTOL (Letunic & Bork, 2024). Statistical analyses were performed using PAST software (Hammer et al., 2001). Data visualization, including bar plots, jitter plots and correlation matrices was conducted using SRplot (Tang et al., 2023) and ImageGP platforms (Chen et al., 2022).

3. Results

3.1. Characterization of the study material and size distribution of analyzed particles

A total of 74 plastic particles naturally occurring in the environment were successfully collected. Samples were retrieved from six different locations on the Pilica River and from eight wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) of varying sizes (small, medium, and large) discharging into the Pilica River catchment (Figure 1A). The physicochemical analysis indicated that the wastewater samples showed lower dissolved oxygen (DO) levels ($0.36\text{--}5.45\text{ mg/L}$), higher electrical conductivity (EC) ($744\text{--}1792.5\text{ }\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), and greater salinity ($0.36\text{--}0.91\text{ g/L}$) than the river samples: DO: $3.97\text{--}7.95\text{ mg/L}$; EC: $370.9\text{--}418.9\text{ }\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$; salinity: $0.18\text{--}0.20\text{ g/L}$. Temperature varied between 19.2°C and 28.0°C , with the warmest samples recorded in river environments (Table S4).

A significantly higher number of particles were recovered from WWTP sites ($n=60$) compared to the river ($n=14$). The collected particles varied in shape, color, size, and thickness, and most demonstrated visible biofilm formation (Figure 1B, Figure S2). FTIR analysis classified the particles into ten different polymer types, with polypropylene ($n=31$) and polyethylene ($n=28$) being the most dominant (Figure

2A). The size of the collected particles ranged from 63.84 mm to 1.74 mm, encompassing macro-, meso-, and microplastic fractions (Figure 2B). Particles collected from wastewater (mean length=9.62 mm) were significantly smaller than those retrieved from the river (mean length=22.81 mm).

Figure 2 Characterization of collected plastic particles: **A** – Number and types of plastic particles collected at each sampling site, presented both individually and according to type, i.e. wastewater or river. **B** – Size distribution of collected plastic particles, with the smallest fraction i.e. microplastics highlighted.

3.2. Colonization of Plastic Particles by Psychrophilic, Mesophilic, and Potentially Antibiotic-Resistant Bacteria

All 30 plastic particles selected for microbiological analysis were found to carry heterotrophic bacteria capable of growth at 22 °C and 37 °C: of these, 18 were retrieved from treated wastewater and 12 from river water. A number of these were microplastic fragments (Figure 3). The number of bacteria ranged from 25 to 7.27×10^4 CFU/piece (mean: 2.31×10^4) growing at 22 °C, and from 65 to 8.60×10^4 CFU/piece (mean: 2.30×10^4) at 37 °C. In addition, 28 of the 30 plastic particles harboured bacteria capable of growth in the presence of carbapenem antibiotics (Carba medium), with abundances ranging from 0 to 2.01×10^4 CFU per particle (mean: 3.57×10^3); no growth on Carba medium was observed in one wastewater sample (12.6.W) and one river sample (11.1.R).

Due to substantial variation in the size of individual particles, all bacterial counts were normalized to estimated particle surface area (CFU/mm²), which allowed for a more accurate representation of colonization heterogeneity across the plastic fragments. The density of bacterial colonization on plastic particles cultured at 22 °C ranged from 3.73 to 1.60×10^4 CFU/mm² (mean: 1.44×10^3), compared to 9.71 to 1.08×10^4 CFU/mm² (mean: 1.32×10^3) at 37 °C. Bacterial densities ranged from 0 to 1.70×10^3 CFU/mm² (mean: 2.17×10^2) on the Carba-selective media (Figure 3).

A strong positive correlation was detected between the occurrence of all three analyzed bacterial groups (Table S5). Plastic particles harboring greater total numbers of bacteria also exhibited higher colonization densities, with a strong and significant correlation observed between CFU/piece and CFU/mm² (Table S5). However, no significant correlation was observed between particle size or surface area and the absolute number of bacteria present on the surface. On the contrary, a significant negative correlation was found between particle size and colonization density (CFU/mm²), particularly for bacteria cultured at 37 °C and those grown on Carba-selective medium, indicating that larger particles tend to be less densely colonized (Table S5).

Figure 3 Quantitative characterization of heterotrophic bacteria cultured from plastispheres and images of the microbologically analyzed plastics. The bar graph presents summary data for individual plastic particles, including particle length, estimated surface area, and the abundance of heterotrophic bacteria capable of growth at 22 °C, 37 °C, and on selective medium supplemented with carbapenem. To the right of the bar graphs, the plastic type is indicated, and a colored circle denotes the classification by size. Microplastic particles (MP1-5) are marked with red text and visualized on the left side of the panel. The remaining plastics (meso- and macroplastics) are presented on the right side. The particle size classification is also indicated in the top left corner.

3.3. Taxonomic composition of culturable bacteria and co-occurrence patterns in plastispheres

Among the bacterial colonies cultivated on culture media, a total of 199 were selected for further microbiological analyses, *viz.* 97 isolated from river-derived particles and 102 from wastewater; of these 147 were grown on TSA medium (n=69 at 22°C; n=78 at 37°C) and 52 on Carba medium (Table S1). Out of the analyzed isolates, 129 were successfully identified to the species level and 70 to the genus level (Figure S4). Representatives of the genera *Aeromonas* (119/199) and *Pseudomonas* (52/199) were dominant, together accounting for 85.92% of all analyzed bacterial strains isolated from plastispheres. Among *Aeromonas* spp., six unique species were successfully identified: *A. hydrophila*, *A. veronii*, *A. punctata*, *A. bestiarum*, *A. salmonicida*, and *A. sobria*. Similarly, six species were identified within the genus *Pseudomonas* spp.: *P. putida*, *P. mosselii*, *P. alcaligenes*, *P. oleovorans*, *P. gessardii*, and *P. toyotomiensis* (Figure S4). These two genera were prevalent among the isolates cultured from plastic particles collected from both wastewater and river environments (Figure 4A), all sampling sites (Figure 4C) and polymer types (Figure 4D), also occurring on the smallest particles (microplastics).

Collectively, *Aeromonas* spp. and *Pseudomonas* spp. frequently co-occurred on the same particle, alongside other less frequently identified taxa. (Figure 4B). These included Gram-negative genera such as *Enterobacter* (*E. cloace*), *Acinetobacter* (*A. johnsonii*, *A. pittii*), *Citrobacter*, *Ectopseudomonas* (*E. chengduensis*), *Stenotrophomonas* (*S. maltophilia*), and *Comamonas* (*C. aquatica*), and Gram-positive genera such as *Streptococcus* (*S. gallolyticus*, *S. salivarius*) and *Staphylococcus* (*S. lugdunensis*) (Figure S4). Several of these taxa exhibited source-specific occurrence patterns (i.e. wastewater vs. river) (Figure 4A), despite being detected on particles from various sampling sites and polymer types (Figure 4 C, D). The highest specificity was observed for the genus *Acinetobacter*, which was commonly detected on particles from wastewater (samples from four treatment plant sites), while being absent on those from river water.

Figure 4 Taxonomic composition of cultured isolates (A, B, C, D) and antibiotic resistance analysis of the isolated strains (E): **A** – Distribution of identified bacterial strains, categorized by sample source, number of analyzed plastic particles (piece), sampling sites (site), and plastic types. **B**- Co-occurrence network diagram showing relationships between bacterial strains found on the same plastic particle. Links between taxa indicate co-detection on a single particle; link thickness reflects the frequency of co-occurrence, node size and label size reflect weight. Detected modules within the network are marked **C** – Percentage distribution of detected taxa at the genus level by plastic type. **D** – Percentage distribution of detected taxa at the genus level by plastic type. **E** – Dendrogram based on 16S rRNA gene sequence similarity among isolates exhibiting inhibition zones <19 mm when tested with imipenem. Metadata related to the isolates are included, along with susceptibility test results for the following antibiotics: PRL – piperacillin, SXT – trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole, CIP – ciprofloxacin, ATM – aztreonam, CAZ – ceftazidime, IMP – imipenem. Connections on the dendrogram indicate shared origin of isolates (i.e. from the same plastic particle).

3.4. Antibiotic resistance of bacteria isolated from plastic particles and their genetic determinants of resistance

Antibiotic resistance analysis revealed the presence of carbapenem-resistant strains within the studied plastisphere communities. Of the 199 analyzed isolates, phenotypic resistance to carbapenems was confirmed in 30 cases, of which 20 originated from riverine plastisphere samples and 10 from wastewater (Figure 4E). Interestingly, only 58% (30/52) of the strains initially isolated from media supplemented with carbapenems successfully passed a subsequent resistance confirmation step based on phenotypic disc diffusion assay. Carbapenem-resistant bacteria were isolated from a total of 15 particles (eight from river samples and seven from wastewater), composed of five different polymers: PE, PP, Nylon/EVA, PS and PET (Figure 4E, Table S2). The carbapenem-resistant isolates were classified into five different species: *Aeromonas hydrophila*, *A. veronii*, *A. salmonicida*, *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia*, and *Pseudomonas putida*.

In several cases, resistance to imipenem co-occurred with resistance to additional antibiotics included in the phenotypic panel. Notably, a number of multidrug-resistant (MDR) strains were identified. For example, *Aeromonas hydrophila* isolates resistant to up to four tested antibiotics were observed,

consistently including imipenem, ceftazidime, and aztreonam, with optional resistance to sulfamethoxazole/trimethoprim and piperacillin. These MDR strains were detected on plastic particles made of PE, PP, and PET, originating from both wastewater (site 6W) and river environments (sites 17R, 24R and 0R). Importantly, the same plastic particles were found to harbour imipenem-resistant isolates, indicating the coexistence of multiple-resistant strains within individual plastisphere communities. Isolates of *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* exhibited strong growth around imipenem discs, with no visible inhibition zone (Table S2), which is consistent with their intrinsic resistance to carbapenems (Figure 4E).

Despite the use of multiple primer sets targeting a broad range of ARGs known to confer resistance to carbapenems, it was frequently not possible to identify the genetic basis of phenotypic resistance, i.e. in 18 of the 30 tested strains. Among those which could be confirmed, all belonged to the genus *Aeromonas*, carrying the metallo- β -lactamase gene *bla*_{C_{phA}/IMI}, which may account for the observed resistance phenotype (Figure 4E).

3.5. Microscopic analysis of plastic biofilms: Scanning electron microscopy and confocal fluorescence microscopy

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) imaging was used to reveal the surface morphology of the collected plastic particles and their accompanying biofilms (Figure 5A). The images showed heterogeneous colonization of the plastic surface, with complex biofilm structures interspersed by visibly uncolonized, darker regions. Colonized zones often displayed localized clusters of microorganisms, and the structure of the biofilm frequently included aggregates of fungal (pieces 2.6.W and 17.3.R), protistan (20.2.W, 22.10.W, 17.3.R), and bacterial cells (all plastic pieces), suggesting spatially-organized microbial communities.

Although the bacterial cells were not directly observable in SEM images, their presence was confirmed using fluorescence-based staining and microscopy (Figure 5B). Bacterial cell size and morphology were found to vary within the plastisphere communities, which was particularly evident in particle 20.2.W. In several samples, bacterial cells appeared in spatially-distinct clusters. Even in the case of particle 20.2.W, a polyurethane fragment heavily and extensively colonized by bacteria, densely packed three-dimensional clusters were observed, indicating areas of intensified colonization. The combination of SEM and confocal microscopy revealed that bacterial cells were generally embedded within the surrounding biofilm matrix, rather than exposed on the plastic surface. This structural arrangement was clearly visualized through the overlay of fluorescence signals and transmitted light in 3D composite images (indicated as “3D” in Figure 5B). In the case of particle 22.10.W, bacterial cells were observed

Figure 5 Biofilm observations on plastic particles using scanning electron microscopy (A) and confocal laser scanning fluorescence microscopy (B). SEM images are presented at different magnifications. Confocal images include signal channels for SYTO-9 and propionium iodine with surface light imaging and 3D surface reconstruction.

within deeper layers of the biofilm; despite having lower intensity, the fluorescence signals penetrating the outer matrix revealed the presence of subsurface bacterial clusters not detectable by SEM alone. The outer surface appeared homogeneous and smooth, with diatom cells visibly integrated into the matrix,

further highlighting the stratified architecture of the biofilm. On particle 2.6.W, strong fluorescence signals from bacterial clusters were obscured in the 3D visualization by overlying structural elements covering the cells from above.

Interestingly particle 2.6.W was found to present elongated, hyphae-like structures with well-defined attachment points to the plastic surface under SEM and confocal microscopy; in addition, similar structures was noted under light microscopy for particle 2.8.W (Figure 6). Both particles were isolated from the same site (WWTP 2W). This fungal organism dominated the surface of the examined particles : a thick polyethylene particle and a thin polypropylene film. Both cases were characterized by well-defined attachment points, distinct v-shape branching, an oval-shaped potential sporangium and dense net-like networks, suggesting that the same fungal species was present in both (Figure 6). Dense networks of hyphae embedded in an extracellular matrix were visible, particularly in the SEM images. Confocal microscopy confirmed the presence of DNA within potential spore-like structures (Figure S5), which corresponded well to the structures localized by light microscopy (Figure 6). Individual hyphae can also be seen to merge into larger, thicker structures (Figure S6), forming dense, net-like networks enveloping the plastic surface (Figure S7).

The analysis of biofilm suspensions detached from the plastic surfaces found the environment of the sample site to have an influence (site-specific) on the composition of its plastsphere community. Microscope observations of Gram-stained biofilm preparations revealed the presence of identical flagellated protists (micro-predators) in the plastsphere of samples from WWTP 6W. In addition, diatom cells were frequently observed on particles retrieved from site 22W, regardless of the plastic polymer type (Figure S8).

Figure 6 Characteristics of the fungus observed on particles from wastewater (site 2W), presenting distinctive morphological features seen under both electron and fluorescence microscopy (top), as well as light microscopy (bottom). ECM - extracellular matrix

4. Discussion

Our findings offer new insights into the composition of native plastsphere communities in freshwater and wastewater environments. The present study was conducted within a hydrologically-connected river-wastewater system, covering multiple sites across freshwater and treated wastewater environments. By collecting samples from across such a diverse base, it was possible to gain insights into plastsphere communities under different but environmentally-linked conditions, thus reflecting real-world exposure scenarios. These findings provide natural insights into plastsphere development and community assembly that cannot be captured by artificial *in situ* deployments or controlled

microcosm experiments. Although this approach did not allow for control over the type and quantity of recovered plastic debris, our results indicate that polyethylene and polypropylene predominated among the collected particles; this is in line with their global prevalence in plastic production and total environment (Jaszczyszyn et al., 2025) and aquatic litter pollution (Schwarz et al., 2019), ensuring the broader relevance of our findings.

To assess the ecological significance of plastic particles and evaluate their role as vectors of microorganisms, it is first necessary to determine the degree of microbial colonization on their surface. The colonization values we obtained, based on the total heterotrophic bacterial count, align with previous data acquired in aquatic environments, although literature data tends to vary considerably, reflecting variation in both environmental conditions and study design (Lear et al., 2022; Liang et al., 2023; Monràs-Riera et al., 2024). These disparities highlight the influence of artificially-introduced versus naturally-aged plastics, on colonization outcomes, and variability in biofilm detachment methods (Stevenson et al., 2023). As such, our findings represent one of the first detailed assessments of plastisphere colonization in river and wastewater, thus providing new insights based on natural, hydrologically-linked environments.

In this study, we employed a culture-dependent analytical approach using chromogenic media targeted at the detection and isolation of Carbapenem-Resistant Enterobacteriaceae (CRE), which did not yield the expected results. Despite the abundant, typical growth observed on the chromogenic medium containing the antibiotic, we failed to detect any CRE isolate. Although we successfully identified some isolates belonging to the Enterobacteriaceae family, they did not exhibit carbapenem resistance. To our surprise, even when selecting colonies with the characteristic color indicating presumptive CRE, their identity was not confirmed as Enterobacteriaceae, but rather as members of the Aeromonadaceae and Pseudomonadaceae families. Similar conclusions were reached by other researchers utilizing mSuperCARBA medium to study wastewater (Cameron et al., 2025), where 0% of the pink (presumptive *E. coli*) colonies were identified as *E. coli*. It appears that the main issue lies in the abundance of Aeromonadaceae and Pseudomonadaceae in the studied environments. These taxa may constitute the main pool of carbapenem-resistant bacteria in wastewater and rivers (Cameron et al., 2025; Drk et al., 2023; Foxman et al., 2025; Mathys et al., 2019; Tacão et al., 2015). while simultaneously retaining the ability to grow on chromogenic media meant to be selective and differential for Enterobacteriales (Cameron et al., 2025). This severely complicates the ability to reliably detect CRE by culture, both in aquatic medium and aquatic plastispheres. We observed in our study that the emergence of carbapenem-resistant/tolerant strains correlated strongly with the total culturable bacterial counts in the plastispheres. This suggests that these group are stable components of the general plastisphere community rather than a result of colonization by allochthonous drug-resistant strains, such as fecal bacteria. This phenomenon seems widespread, as we observed it across numerous particles retrieved from both the river (various sections) and wastewater (various treatment plants), and across different polymer types.

These observations were complemented by both molecular analyses aimed at detecting carbapenem resistance genes and phenotypic resistance assays. Curiously, only some of the isolates grown on the selective Carba medium (56%) were confirmed to be carbapenem resistant using the standard disk diffusion method. This indicates a possible tolerance to the antibiotic among plastisphere bacteria rather than resistance. This phenomenon may also be related to the nature of the commonly-detected CphA mechanism, which does not always produce classic results in phenotypic resistance assessment (Hilt et al., 2020). Furthermore, despite the use of multiple primer sets targeting both common and rare carbapenem resistance genes, some carbapenem-resistant isolates remained negative for ARG identification. This collective observation may account for the dominance of the Gram-negative rods *Aeromonas* spp. and *Pseudomonas* spp., within carbapenemase resistant/tolerant bacteria in plastisphere: these taxa are known to possess efflux pumps and porin loss associated with multidrug resistance and antibiotic tolerance without necessarily involving the classical ARGs targeted in this

study (non-enzyme-mediated resistance mechanisms) (Laborda et al., 2021; Lo et al., 2021). This findings are particularly noteworthy given that the physicochemical properties of plastics allow them to adsorb a variety of environmental pollutants, including antibiotics (Samaei et al., 2025). Such contamination may create unique microhabitats characterized by more intense selective pressures, thus fostering the emergence and evolution of bacteria with enhanced resistance and tolerance profiles and metabolic activity. These microenvironments, shaped by the combined effects of biofilm formation, pollutant accumulation, and microbial interactions, represent important but still underexplored systems that warrant further investigation.

While cases of CRE carrying clinically relevant carbapenemases in plastispheres are documented via culture (Silva et al., 2023, 2024) the studies relied on plastic particles artificially introduced into the environment. Despite the lack of success in isolating CRE, the present study, native plastispheres were found to harbor multiple antibiotic-resistant strains affiliated with taxa of clinical and environmental concern. Among the most relevant isolates were *Pseudomonas putida*, resistant to carbapenems, and MDR carbapenemase-producing *Aeromonas hydrophila*; both pose potential risks to fish and other aquatic organisms known to ingest plastic particles (Sulaiman et al., 2023). Molecular analysis revealed that neither imipenem-resistant *Aeromonas* spp. nor *Pseudomonas putida* isolates carried typical high-risk carbapenemase genes such as *bla_{KPC}* or *bla_{NDM}*. Instead, imipenem resistance in *Aeromonas* was associated with the chromosomally encoded, non-mobile *bla_{CphA}* gene - an intrinsic mechanism characteristic of this genus; its presence may complicate clinical treatment and mask clinically relevant resistance during routine diagnostic testing (Hilt et al., 2020). Additionally, a number of wastewater plastispheres contained *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia*, whose carbapenem resistance is intrinsically linked to the β -lactamase genes *bla_{L1}* and *bla_{L2}* (Sapula et al., 2024). This species is an emerging global opportunistic pathogen, intrinsically resistant to multiple antibiotics, and increasingly implicated in difficult-to-treat infections such as pneumonia and bacteremia (Bhaumik et al., 2023). In one isolate, the species also included acquired resistance to trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole, the first-line therapy for *S. maltophilia* infections (Mojica et al., 2022). This extended resistance range is particularly concerning given the clinical relevance of the taxon, being implicated in nosocomial infections and treatment failures. Plastisphere-mediated dissemination of resistance thus represents an emerging threat at the intersection of environmental and public health.

The insights gained from the cultivation-based methods were supplemented by microscopy. Electron microscopy revealed a remarkable degree of complexity and diversity within the biofilms. Interestingly, in some samples from both river and wastewater environments, the plastic particles presented prominent fungi, forming a network that bound extracellular substances and served as a structural core for other organisms. A particularly intriguing finding was the presence of a strongly expansive fungus, firmly attached to plastic surfaces via specialized structures, capable of colonizing different polymer types within the same wastewater sample. On other particles, the biofilm appeared flatter and smoother, without hyphal structures. This may indicate different dynamics and models of biofilm development (Amaral-Zettler et al., 2020). The surface observations were complemented by fluorescence imaging, which highlighted the exact spatial distribution of bacteria within the biofilms. Previously, such observations were limited to *in situ* marine (Cheng et al., 2021; Hoshihara et al., 2025; Khandare et al., 2021; Schlundt et al., 2020; Zhao et al., 2021) and lake experiments (Di Pippo et al., 2023); as such, our present findings represent the first such observations of natural wastewater and riverine plastispheres.

Scanning Electron Microscopy imaging revealed the structural complexity of the plastispheres, clearly showing the presence of diverse organisms, including diatoms and fungi. However, fluorescence imaging proved to be the key tool for observing bacteria within the plastispheres. SEM alone was not effective for observing bacterial cells, as they were frequently hidden in the deeper layers of the biofilm. The combination of both methods demonstrated that field-collected samples were characterized by uncolonized areas and local bacterial clusters, with biofilm expansion occurring gradually. Notably,

within these densely-colonized particles, the presence of bacterial clusters may facilitate close cell-to-cell contact, potentially promoting microbial interactions. A promising direction for future research would be to determine the taxonomic composition of these bacterial aggregates using fluorescently-labeled probes; for example, CLASI-FISH (combinatorial labeling and spectral imaging - fluorescence in situ hybridization) enables high-resolution, multiplexed identification of microbial taxa directly within biofilms (Schlundt et al., 2020). This approach will allow researchers to decipher the taxonomic richness of the observed bacterial clusters and direct observations toward clinically significant (e.g., Enterobacteriaceae), as well as non-culturable taxa that may reside within plastispheres.

A limitation of this study is the exclusive use of culture-dependent methods, which do not capture the full microbial diversity of plastispheres, particularly non-culturable taxa. True taxonomic diversity, which may exceed of the total community, can only be accurately ascertained through metagenome sequencing based on the 16S rRNA gene fragment. However, this culture-based approach allowed us to focus on viable, metabolically active bacteria and specifically identify the carbapenem-resistant fraction of culturable isolates. Another limitation concerns the unequal number and size of particles retrieved from river and wastewater environments, as well as the inability to control the precise duration of their exposure in the respective medium. Consequently, it is challenging to definitively ascertain whether observed differences in colonization are solely due to the nature of the medium, the time the particles spent in the medium, the size and type of the recovered material, or the history and development process of the biofilms. Therefore, due to these inherent complexities, this study did not focus on comparing colonization values between polymer types, sampling sites, or environments. The obtained CFU-based values are thus primarily exploratory, reflecting important natural colonization states and providing a crucial baseline for observations conducted on artificially introduced plastics. This approach illustrates how plastisphere colonization unfolds under genuine environmental conditions.

5. Conclusions and future research

The plastisphere biofilms found on particles retrieved from river and processed wastewater are structurally diverse, dynamically assembled, and exhibit inconsistent bacterial loads. This observed variability indicates that colonization dynamics are complex and context-dependent. Notably, plastisphere communities are also reliant on certain fungi, which contribute to the structural framework and show specialization in colonizing plastic particles. The presented observations from native plastispheres enhance our understanding of naturally aged plastic debris and may serve as a reference point for studies based on *in situ* experiments.

Our study demonstrates that carbapenem resistance in native river and wastewater plastispheres was predominantly driven by intrinsic mechanisms, including enzyme expression (e.g., CphA) and possible non-enzyme-mediated resistance/tolerance mechanisms (e.g., efflux pumps and porin loss), in common Gram-negative rods (*Aeromonas* spp., *Pseudomonas* spp., *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia*), rather than the prevalence of mobile, clinically significant carbapenemases. This reliance on intrinsic mechanisms may complicate the analysis and reliable isolation of clinically significant CRE in plastispheres.

Studying naturally aged plastic debris offers ecologically grounded insights into plastisphere development but remains methodologically challenging. Improved and standardized *in situ* sampling methods are needed to reliably monitor native plastisphere biofilms in aquatic environments. Our findings highlight promising directions for future research, including the *in situ* identification of bacterial consortia within biofilms using advanced fluorescence-based techniques, which will enable the detailed taxonomic resolution of observed bacterial clusters.

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7. Author Contribution Statement

Rolbiecki Damian: Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – Original draft, Visualization. **Jaszczyszyn Katarzyna:** Investigation. **Wawrocki Sebastian:** Investigation. **Józwiak Piotr:** Investigation. **Gajewska Joanna:** Investigation. **Czatkowska Małgorzata:** Investigation. **Harnisz Monika:** Resources, Writing – Review. **Kiedrzyńska Edyta:** Funding Acquisition, Resources, Supervision, Writing – Review.

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